

MIGRATION PROCESSES AND THE LABOR MARKET IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract: *This article examines the impact of international and intra-EU migration on the functioning of the European Union labor market. It analyzes key demographic and economic trends, including the structure of migrant labor, employment participation, economic activity, and the effects on productivity and wage distribution. Special attention is given to institutional mechanisms for migration regulation and migrant integration, such as the European Migration Agenda and directives on legal labor migration. Based on Eurostat and OECD statistical data, the study highlights the multifaceted effects of migration on labor market sustainability, addressing labor shortages and ensuring socio-economic stability in the context of population aging and structural changes.*

Keywords: *Migration, labor migrants, labor market, European Union, migrant integration, population aging, institutional regulation, economic sustainability.*

YEVROPA ITTIFOQIDA MIGRATSIYA JARAYONLARI VA MEHNAT BOZORI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada xalqaro va Yevropa Ittifoqi ichidagi migratsiyaning Yevropa Ittifoqi mehnat bozorining faoliyatiga ta’siri tahlil qilinadi. Unda asosiy demografik va iqtisodiy tendentsiyalar, jumladan migrant mehnat kuchining tuzilishi, bandlikda ishtirok etish, iqtisodiy faollik hamda mahsuldorlik va ish haqi taqsimotiga ta’sirlar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Xususan, Yevropa migratsiya kun tartibi va qonuniy mehnat migratsiyasi bo‘yicha direktivalar kabi migratsiyani tartibga solish va migrantlarni integratsiya qilish bo‘yicha institutsional*

mexanizmlarga alohida e’tibor qaratiladi. Eurostat va OECD statistik ma’lumotlariga asoslanib, tadqiqot migratsiyaning mehnat bozorining barqarorligiga ko‘p qirrali ta’sirini, mehnat kuchi tanqisligini bartaraf etish va aholi qarishi hamda strukturaviy o‘zgarishlar sharoitida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta’minlashni yoritadi.

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Migratsiya, mehnat migrantlari, mehnat bozori, Yevropa Ittifoqi, migrant integratsiyasi, aholi qarishi, institutsional tartibga solish, iqtisodiy barqarorlik.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of deepening globalization, international migration remains one of the key factors transforming the global economy and labor markets. According to the latest estimates by the United Nations, by mid-2024, the number of international migrants worldwide reached 304 million people, accounting for approximately 3.7% of the global population and nearly doubling the 1990 figure (154 million) (Figure 1)¹. At the same time, more than half of all migrants (about 56%) reside in countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), including major economic centers such as the United States and the member states of the European Union². New permanent migration flows to OECD countries remained high in 2024, amounting to approximately 6.2 million new permanent immigrants, although they showed a slight decline compared to the previous year³.

Labor migration also remains an important element of global migration processes, despite its decline in a number of developed countries in 2024: the overall inflow of labor migrants decreased by approximately 21% compared to 2023, yet it still significantly exceeds the levels observed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic⁴. In addition, the number of individuals granted humanitarian status in OECD countries increased by 23%, reflecting a rise in displacement driven by conflicts and crises⁵.

¹ United Nations (2024). International Migrant Stock 2024: Key facts and figures. UN DESA/POP/2024/DC/NO. 13. https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa.pd/files/undesa_pd_2025_intlmigstock_2024_key_facts_and_figures_advance-unedited.pdf

² Recent developments in international migration movements and labour market inclusion of immigrants/OECD (2025), International Migration Outlook 2025, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ae26c893-en>.

³ Executive summary/OECD (2025), International Migration Outlook 2025, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ae26c893-en>.

⁴ Recent developments in international migration movements and labour market inclusion of immigrants/OECD (2025), International Migration Outlook 2025, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ae26c893-en>.

⁵ Recent developments in international migration movements and labour market inclusion of immigrants/OECD (2025), International Migration Outlook 2025, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ae26c893-en>.

Figure 1. Number of international migrants worldwide and their share of the global population, 1990-2024⁶

Global migration processes have numerous socio-economic consequences, including impacts on demographic structures, labor markets, social protection systems, and the fiscal balances of receiving countries. In this context, the European Union occupies a special position as a region that combines the role of a major “hub” of international migration flows with a unique institutional system of free movement of labor within the union. As of 2024, Europe remained the region with the largest concentration of international migrants worldwide (approximately 94 million people), highlighting the significance of migration for the socio-economic dynamics of the EU and its labor markets⁷.

MAIN PART

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⁶ United Nations (2024). International Migrant Stock 2024: Key facts and figures. UN DESA/POP/2024/DC/NO. 13. https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa.pd/files/undesa_pd_2025_intlmigstock_2024_key_facts_and_figures_advance-unedited.pdf

⁷ Там же.

Table 1. Key Indicators of Migration and Asylum in Europe (2023-2024):

Indicator	Value/Data
Share of foreign nationals in the EU population	~10%
– of which citizens of other EU countries	3.1%
– of which non-EU citizens	6.4%
Immigrants to the EU from non-EU countries	4.4 million
Decrease in immigration from non-EU countries (compared to 2022)	–18%
Emigrants from the EU to non-EU countries	~1.5 million
Positive net migration (immigration – emigration)	~+3 million
Intra-EU migration (between EU countries)	~1.5 million
Leading countries in intra-EU migration	Germany, Spain, Romania, Netherlands, France
Total number of people granted protection (asylum)	438,000 persons
Primary asylum applications	~913,000
Countries with the highest number of applications (EU)	Germany, Spain, Italy, France
Main applicant nationality groups	Syria, Venezuela, Afghanistan
People found without legal status	919,000
Main countries with irregularly present migrants	Germany, France, Italy

Source: Compiled on the basis of Migration and asylum in Europe – 2025 <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/migration-2025>

According to Eurostat’s “Migration and Asylum in Europe 2025”, the following key features of migration processes can currently be identified in the European Union (Figure 2)⁸:

1. Migration remains a key driver of demographic growth in the EU. Despite a decline in immigration from non-EU countries in 2023 (–18% compared to 2022), overall net migration remains positive (around +3 million people). This confirms that migration compensates for natural population decline in many EU countries.

2. The structure of migrants is characterized by the predominance of non-EU citizens. Approximately two-thirds of all foreign nationals in the EU are citizens of third countries. This increases the importance of migration policy, integration measures, and regulation of access to the labor market.

3. Intra-European mobility remains stable. Migration within the EU (about 1.5 million people per year) continues to be concentrated in economically

⁸ Migration and asylum in Europe - 2025. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/migration-2025>
www.sharqjurnali.uz DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20292447

stronger countries (Germany, Spain, France), reflecting differences in employment opportunities and income levels.

4. Pressure on the asylum system persists. The number of primary asylum applications in 2024 remains high (around 913,000), with the main burden falling on a limited number of countries. This indicates an uneven distribution of migration flows within the EU.

5. The issue of irregular migration remains relevant. Nearly 1 million people identified as being without legal status point to a gap between the scale of migration flows and the administrative capacity to manage and control them.

Overall, Eurostat data show that migration for the EU is both a resource for economic and demographic development and a source of institutional and social challenges, which requires a coordinated pan-European policy approach.

Figure 2. Main Trends in Migration Processes in the EU (2025))⁹

Migration processes in the EU are characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity and include several key dimensions: intra-EU mobility, immigration from third countries, as well as temporary and seasonal labor migration. Internal migration between EU member states is traditionally directed from countries with lower income and employment levels (Central and Eastern Europe, Southern Europe) toward more economically developed countries of Western and Northern Europe, such as Germany, France, the Netherlands, and the Scandinavian countries¹⁰.

⁹ Migration and asylum in Europe - 2025. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/migration-2025>

¹⁰ Eurostat. Migration and migrant population statistics. -Luxembourg: European Commission, 2023. -URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat> (дата обращения: 10.01.2026).

Forced migration related to armed conflicts and humanitarian crises deserves particular attention. The migration crisis of 2015-2016 became an important turning point for EU migration policy, revealing the vulnerability of existing mechanisms for the distribution of migrants and exerting a significant impact on national labor markets and social protection systems¹¹.

The formation of a single European labor market is closely linked to the implementation of the fundamental principle of the free movement of labor, enshrined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. This principle grants EU citizens the right to move freely, reside, and engage in employment in the territory of any Member State without discrimination on the basis of nationality¹². As a result, a specific model of intra-EU migration has emerged, combining elements of internal mobility and international labor movement.

Contemporary migration processes have a significant impact on the functioning of the European Union’s labor market, shaping employment dynamics, the structure of the workforce, and the level of economic activity. According to Eurostat, in 2024, the employment rate of the population aged 20-64 in the EU reached 75.8%, representing the highest level recorded since the start of statistical observations in 2009¹³. In 2025, the positive trend persisted: in the first half of the year, the employment rate increased to 76.1-76.2%, indicating the high resilience of the European labor market amid global economic uncertainty¹⁴.

A low unemployment rate also characterizes the current state of the EU labor market. In 2024-2025, the unemployment rate fluctuated within the range of 5.7-5.8%, remaining close to historical lows¹⁵. At the same time, a certain amount of unused labor potential persists: the so-called “labor market slack” in the EU amounts to around 11%, reflecting the presence of individuals who are partially or potentially engaged in the labor market¹⁶. Under conditions of demographic aging and a shrinking working-age population, these trends further increase the importance of migration as a source of labor force replenishment.

¹¹ European Commission. A European Agenda on Migration. -Brussels: European Commission, COM (2015) 240 final, 2015. -23 p.

¹² Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). Consolidated version. -Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016. -358 p.

¹³ Eurostat. Employment annual statistics 2024. Statistics Explained, 11 Apr. 2025. -14 p. URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDF/cache/88651.pdf>

¹⁴ Eurostat. EU’s employment rate reached almost 76 % in 2024 / Eurostat News Release, 15 Apr. 2025. -1 p. URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20250415-1>

¹⁵ Eurostat. Unemployment statistics 2024-2025. Statistics Explained, data extracted May 2025. -Luxembourg, May 2025. -20-30 p. URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDF/cache/6942.pdf>

¹⁶ Eurostat. Labour market slack statistics 2025. -Statistics Explained / News Releases, 2025. -Luxembourg: Eurostat, 2025. -URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news>

Table 2. Migration and the EU Labor Market in 2024

Indicator	Value
Employment rate of the population aged 20–64	75.8%
Unemployment rate	5.7–5.8%
Labour market slack (reserve of labor force)	≈11%
Share of migrants in the working-age population	12.6%
Economic activity rate of migrants	77%
Employment rate among migrants	71%
Share of migrants in part-time employment	22.2%
Share of migrants working below their qualifications (over-qualification)	High

Source: based on Eurostat, European Commission, and OECD Migration statistics

From the perspective of economic theory, migration has a direct impact on the labor market by altering the supply of labor, the structure of employment, and the level of competition among workers. Under conditions of demographic aging and a decline in the working-age population in most EU countries, migration is regarded as one of the key instruments for sustaining economic activity and the stability of pension systems¹⁷.

Empirical studies show that labor migrants generally complement rather than displace the native workforce, occupying niches characterized by chronic labor shortages or low attractiveness for the local population¹⁸. This is especially characteristic of low-paid and physically demanding types of work, as well as the personal care services sector. At the same time, highly skilled migrants contribute to the development of the economy’s innovative potential, particularly in the fields of information technology, engineering, and scientific research. Migrants play an increasingly significant role in ensuring the functioning of the European Union’s labor market.

According to estimates by the European Commission, the share of the working-age population born outside the EU reached 12.6% in 2024, reflecting the growing contribution of migration to the region’s labor force structure¹⁹. According to OECD data, the economic activity rate of migrants in EU countries exceeds 77%,

¹⁷ United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA). World Population Prospects 2022: Summary of Results. -New York: United Nations, 2022. -52 p.

¹⁸ Borjas, G. J. Labor Economics. -8th ed. -New York: McGraw-Hill Education, 2020. -704 p.

¹⁹ European Commission. Migration, mobility and the EU labour market. Economy-and-Finance Special Topic, 17 Nov. 2025. -Luxembourg: European Commission, 2025. -URL: https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/migration-mobility-and-eu-labour-market_en

while about 71% of migrants are employed in the economy, which is comparable to the figures observed among the native population²⁰.

Immigration from third countries plays an increasingly significant role in shaping the EU labor force. Key regions of origin of migrants include the Middle East, North Africa, South Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa. At the same time, the structure of migration is heterogeneous: alongside highly skilled specialists, there is an inflow of low-skilled labor employed in sectors experiencing labor shortages²¹. Such sectors include construction, agriculture, care for the elderly and the sick, transport, as well as the hospitality and restaurant industry²². In these segments of the labor market, migrants perform a compensatory function by complementing rather than displacing the local workforce. In this way, migration contributes to maintaining production chains and the resilience of the service sector, especially under conditions of limited domestic labor supply.

The impact of migration on unemployment levels in EU countries is limited and generally short-term in nature. Most studies by the OECD and the European Commission confirm that the long-term effect of migration on the employment of the native population is neutral or moderately positive²³. This is because an increase in the supply of labor is accompanied by an expansion of aggregate demand, higher consumption, and the creation of new jobs.

Despite the high level of participation in the labor market, the employment conditions of migrants in the EU differ from those of citizens of host countries. Eurostat statistics show that migrants are significantly more often employed under temporary contracts and in part-time jobs. In 2024, the share of migrants from third countries working part-time amounted to 22.2%, whereas the corresponding figure among EU citizens was considerably lower²⁴.

In addition, migrants more often face the problem of a mismatch between their level of qualifications and the positions they hold. The phenomenon of “skills underutilization” (over-qualification) remains a characteristic feature of migrant

²⁰ OECD. International Migration Outlook 2025. Paris: OECD Publishing, 3 ноября 2025. -350 с. DOI: 10.1787/ae26c893-en. URL:

https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/international-migration-outlook-2025_355ae9fd.html

²¹ OECD. International Migration Outlook 2023. -Paris: OECD Publishing, 2023. -352 p. DOI: 10.1787/29f23edc-en.

²² ICMPD (International Centre for Migration Policy Development). Migration Outlook 2025. Vienna: ICMPD, 2025. -60-80 с.

²³ OECD. The Economic Impact of Migration. -Paris: OECD Publishing, 2014. -122 p. DOI: 10.1787/9789264218313-en.

²⁴ Eurostat. Migrant integration statistics - employment conditions. Luxembourg: Eurostat, 2024. -20-30 с. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migrant_integration_statistics_%E2%80%93_93_employment_conditions

employment, especially during the first years of residence in the host country²⁵. This feature affects the structure of the EU labor market by contributing to employment segmentation and reinforcing the differentiation of jobs in terms of pay levels and employment stability.

One of the most debated aspects of migration is its impact on wage levels. Theoretically, an inflow of migrants may exert downward pressure on wages in low-skilled segments of the labor market. However, under the conditions of well-developed labor market regulation institutions in the EU, including minimum wages, collective bargaining, and social protections, this effect is substantially mitigated²⁶.

Studies by the European Central Bank and the International Labour Organization show that migration may lead to a slight decline in wages in certain sectors; however, at the same time, it contributes to higher labor productivity and increased overall labor market flexibility²⁷. Thus, the impact of migration on overall wage levels in the EU is moderate and structurally differentiated. Wage pressure may be observed in certain low-skilled segments of the labor market; however, in the medium and long term, this effect is offset by productivity growth, expanding demand, and increased economic flexibility²⁸. Moreover, migrants often initially accept employment conditions that subsequently evolve into more stable forms of employment as they integrate into the host society, and the wage gap narrows accordingly: over the first five years, it decreases on average by 10-13 percentage points²⁹.

Thus, statistical data for 2024-2025 confirm that migration is a crucial factor in the resilience of the European Union’s labor market. Under conditions of record-high employment and demographic aging, migrants help fill labor shortages, support the functioning of key sectors, and contribute to maintaining economic activity. At the same time, structural differences in employment conditions and income levels among migrants persist, shaping a complex and multi-layered model of migration’s impact on the EU labor market, which requires comprehensive institutional regulation.

²⁵ Eurostat. Migrant integration statistics - over-qualification. Luxembourg: Eurostat, 2024. -15-25 c. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Migrant_integration_statistics_-_over-qualification

²⁶ International Labour Organization (ILO). Global Wage Report 2022-23: The impact of inflation and COVID-19. - Geneva: ILO, 2022. -164 p.

²⁷ European Central Bank (ECB). Labour mobility and migration in the euro area. -Frankfurt am Main: ECB Occasional Paper Series No. 256, 2021. -48 p.

²⁸ OECD. International Migration Outlook 2025. Paris: OECD Publishing, 2025. -350 p. (DOI: 10.1787/ae26c893-en. URL: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/international-migration-outlook-2025_355ae9fd.html

²⁹ International Labour Organization (ILO). Global Wage Report 2024-2025: The impact of inflation and post-pandemic labour market trends. Geneva: ILO, 2025. -160 c.

CONCLUSION

Migration regulation and the integration of migrants into the labor market are carried out on a multi-level basis, combining supranational EU instruments with the national policies of the Member States. Key initiatives include the “European Agenda on Migration,” directives on legal labor migration, and mechanisms for the recognition of professional qualifications³⁰.

The EU Blue Card system is of particular importance, as it is aimed at attracting highly qualified specialists from third countries. This instrument contributes to strengthening human capital and reducing skills shortages in strategically important sectors of the economy³¹. At the same time, significant differences in approaches to migrant integration persist across the EU, reflecting the specific characteristics of national labor markets and socio-economic models.

It should be noted that migration has a differentiated impact across EU regions. In economically developed regions, migrants contribute to employment growth, the development of urban agglomerations, and the expansion of the tax base. In less developed regions, intra-EU migration may lead to labor outflows and the intensification of territorial disparities³².

At the same time, migration flows stimulate cross-border economic linkages, the formation of business networks, and the diffusion of knowledge. Thus, migration acts not only as a demographic and social phenomenon but also as an important factor in the spatial development of the EU economy.

Overall, migration processes in the European Union are an integral part of the functioning of the regional labor market and exert a comprehensive impact on employment, wages, productivity, and economic growth. Under conditions of demographic aging, migration serves as a key source of labor force replenishment and the maintenance of socio-economic system sustainability. At the same time, the effectiveness of utilizing migration potential largely depends on the quality of institutional regulation, integration policies, and the coherence of actions at both the EU and Member State levels.

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